

ICT IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article defines that using of information and Communication technologies in english language ateaching and learning. Moreover, there are shown the result of using these technologies.

Keywords: *Information and communication technologies, mobile learning, integrated language learning, rural schools*

INTRODUCTION

Now, ICT (Information and Communication Technology) has been used in almost all fields of life, including in education. In education, computer technology has become so essential that the government put ICT as one of the curriculum in Indonesia's education. The utilization of ICT in education has recently started to appeal the potential and significant progress in language learning. It has become a major issue in education world and has been used from preschool through to university that could facilitate students and teacher in teaching and learning process. ICT has been publicized as potentially powerful enabling tools for educational change and reform. The computers play significant role in the learning process especially in learning language. As Hartoyo (2008) stated in his book, a computer is a tool and medium that facilitates people in learning a language, although the effectiveness of learning depends totally on the users. The technology in this era has been grown up not only from the quality but also the efficiency. They are moving fast without any limit from every product. The need of technological innovation has brought the communication revolution and rapid development of technological application in teaching and learning. This technology made contribution on improving language communication in Indonesia. Every school has used the ICT to facilitate the teacher to teach the students in the classroom. Many kinds of application that they use in the classroom improved and enhanced the better lesson.

METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

English language is a necessity of for most people in today's world, while technology development always has a very high and also contributed towards the

development of education, especially English. As English is one of difficult lessons, teacher must create interactive teaching and learning to make students interest. In the history of the development of education, information technology is part of the medium used to convey the message of science to many people, ranging from printing technology a few centuries ago, such as printed books, such as telecommunications to media, voice recorded on tape, video, television, and CD. According to Kent “ICT in education point of view refers to “information and communication Technology (ICT) such as computers, communications facilities and features that variously support teaching, learning and a range of activities in education (QCA Schemes of Work for ICT in Kent Country Council. 2004). Moreover, the term information and Communications Technologies includes technologies in which the computer plays a central role, i.e. Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL), the internet, and variety of generic computer application. The development of information technology, the Internet, directs the history of educational technology in the new groove. Online services in the education of both degree and non-degree are basically providing educational services to users using the Internet as a medium. Online services can be composed of various stages of the process of educational programs such as: registration, test entry, payment, learning, case assignments, case discussions, exams, assessments, discussions, and announcements. Nothing the positive impact of various studies on the use of ICT to support learning in the school, it is a must if the school is not excessive in this country also have the prospect of a future that allows for deploying ICT in supporting learning and they are:

a) Presentation

Some material of language learning such as text-based materials, audio-video needs to present to the learners. Presentation helps learners in understanding the learning material well.

b) Practice

Some of different exercises types are possible to be provided with ICT, incorporating the presentation stimuli in varying combinations of text, audio and video format. ICT also offers the possibility of the analyzing learners’ responses with appropriate feedback.(Hartoyo, 2012:40)

c) Authoring

In applying ICT in language learning, teacher can either purchase ready-made materials or create their own exercise materials using a variety of authoring tools based on Hartoyo (2012:40).

d) Computer-Aided Assessment (CAA)

Computer-Aided Assessment (CAA) is playing an increasingly important role in foreign language teaching and learning. This media used to testing and assessing students understanding after learning some courses.

CONCLUSION

All in all, ICT appears to give both advantages and disadvantages. ICT in language learning reduces the intimacy of students – teacher relationship that it may negatively contributes to students affective feelings in the process of learning. However, ICT appears as a ‘bridge’ to break the distance and ‘survive’ the learning. In case of distance, teachers can use ICT through video conference to enable them teach or monitor the students learning process. Therefore, the development of ICT is seen as a better way of teaching and learning a certain language compared to the existing methods. Through the internet, teacher or learners can obtain as many as possible sources related to the learned – language; such as text, songs, stories, etc. Those sources can contribute as models of the learned – language use in the real context and in a proper manner.

Advantages:

- The information required will be more quickly and easily accessible for educational purposes.
- Innovation in learning is growing in the presence of e-learning innovations that further facilitate the educational process.
- Progress of ICT will also allow the development of virtual classroom or classroom-based teleconference that does not require the educator and learners are in one room.
- System administration in an institution will be more easily and smoothly because of the application of ICT systems.

Disadvantages:

- Progress of ICT will also occur of violation of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) for the easy access to the data that is causing people plagiatis will commit fraud.
- Although the system of the administration of an educational institution like a system without a gap, but if there is a recklessness in running the system would be dangerous.
- One of the negative impact of television is to train children to think short and survive concentrated in a short time (short span of attention).

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